

IMPROVING THE MECHANISM FOR STIMULATING PARTICIPANTS IN THE DISTRIBUTION OF PRODUCTS

Musayeva Shoirazimovna,

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Usmanov Shakhzod Shokhrukhovich

Student, Samarkand Institute of economic and services

Ruzikhulova Nilufar Ulugbekovna

Student, Samarkand Institute of economic and services

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Abstract. *This article discusses the system of product distribution through the retail trade of a range of goods, the proper quality of the goods sold, to better meet the needs of the population, as well as the distribution of responsibility between the participants in the distribution of goods.*

Keywords: *production, product range, quality, distribution, region, dealer, competition.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ МЕХАНИЗМА СТИМУЛИРОВАНИЯ УЧАСТНИКОВ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ПРОДУКЦИИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается система товародвижения через розничную торговлю ассортиментом товаров, надлежащее качество реализуемых товаров, для более полного удовлетворения потребностей населения, а также распределение ответственности между участниками товародвижения. .*

Ключевые слова: *производство, ассортимент, качество, дистрибуция, регион, дилер, конкуренция.*

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, large-scale measures have been taken to develop wholesale and retail trade. Currently, almost every resident has the opportunity to purchase the necessary goods at minimal cost. Manufacturing enterprises are also expanding distribution channels to increase the competitiveness of their products. At the same time, there are a number of goods, the sale of which requires certain marketing efforts from manufacturers. These products include non-alcoholic beverages.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

RESULTS

– An important indicator of the distribution channel of goods is the level of the channel. The higher the level of the channel, the less role the manufacturer plays in it, the more role intermediaries play. On the other hand, the higher the channel level, the closer the product is brought to the end consumer. Therefore, it is important for the manufacturer to organize the distribution channel of the optimal level and ensure a combination of various distribution channels.

- development of the essence of distribution channels of goods and their place in the marketing activities of manufacturing enterprises;

- study of the state of marketing activities in the Uzbek-Czech joint venture "Samarkand-Prague-Beer";
- Study of beer and mineral water distribution channels at the enterprise;
- Studying ways to improve distribution channels and stimulate their participants in the sale of beer;

One of the factors that have a great influence on the quality of trade services for the population is the system of product distribution. The influence of this factor on the efficiency of trade services is carried out through the following mechanisms:

1. The system of distribution through retail trade provides the breadth and depth of the range of goods, which makes it possible to increase the competitiveness of products sold in a trading enterprise and, accordingly, the profitability of trading activities.

2. The system of product distribution through the possibility of updating the range of goods ensures the proper quality of the goods sold, which ultimately leads to a more complete satisfaction of the needs of the population.

3. The system of product distribution through retail trade enterprises determines the length of the distribution channels of goods, which affects the forms of pricing, as well as the distribution of responsibility between the participants in the distribution of goods, and thus affects the volume and structure of retail trade.

Thus, increasing the efficiency of trade services largely depends on the effectiveness of the product distribution system. The indicators of the effectiveness of the product distribution system should include the level of responsibility of manufacturers for the quality, assortment and marketability of goods, as well as ensuring the rights of consumers in terms of creating opportunities for the exchange or return of low-quality goods. In accordance with the indicated indicators, as well as the goals of retail trade in the formation of an assortment of goods, we have identified several schemes for the distribution of products (Fig. 1).

Rice. 1.

The main schemes of product distribution.

According to scheme "A", the manufacturer, through his sales representative, according to direct contracts, delivers his products directly to the shelves. Usually these are goods that have a limited shelf life and are produced in a given region. When using this scheme of goods distribution, the manufacturer bears full responsibility for the range and quality of the supplied goods, guarantees the exchange, return and, in certain cases, the removal of low-quality goods from trade circulation.

Under Scheme B, the manufacturer, through a regional sales representative, sells goods to wholesale intermediaries, who convert the production assortment into a trade assortment and then sell the goods to a retail distribution network. In this scheme, the responsibility of the manufacturer is significantly reduced, since the wholesale buyer, purchasing the goods, makes mutual settlements with them. If a low-quality product is found in a retail network, the possibility of its exchange or return is reduced.

This shortcoming is somewhat compensated in the "B" scheme, since the regional sales representatives, through the official dealer, form the trade assortment. Consequently, the dealer can sell goods directly to the retail trade network, or to wholesale intermediaries who further promote them to the consumer market.

There are groups of goods whose producers do not have their own distribution channels, so their task is to sell goods from finished goods warehouses to wholesale intermediaries who assume obligations to sell goods. So, in the "D" scheme, wholesale intermediaries, through their regional representatives, supply goods to the retail trade network. In this case, even if it is possible to return the goods, the exchange for an equivalent product becomes a difficult task, since at the very initial stage the manufacturer realized the property rights in a deal with a wholesale intermediary.

Similarly, according to the "D" scheme, the manufacturer sells lots of goods to wholesale intermediaries, who then sell it in parts by an independent dealer or sales agent who supply goods to the retail trade network.

To solve the problem of effective product distribution of the company's products, we have developed proposals for the formation of such systems in rural areas, the content of which is as follows:

1. Implementation of an inventory of a retail trade enterprise and determination of its status of the district's social infrastructure. Entrepreneurs must show their interest in fulfilling the mission and strategic goals of improving the quality of trade services for the population when selling products of the Samarkand-Prague-Beer JV. Assortment inventory is a declaration of a retail trade enterprise on ensuring the required assortment minimum for groups of goods. For example, the assumption of obligations to update the assortment, the presence in the assortment of goods of short-term and long-term storage, guarantees of unconditional exchange or contractual relations with JV "Samarkand-Prague-Beer" or suppliers of goods. Thus, a supermarket in a district center, according to its status, must ensure continuous updating of the assortment for all groups of food and non-food products, as well as ensure the conclusion of contracts for the supply of the entire range of consumer goods. An exception may be specialized goods of the joint venture "Samarkand-Prague-Beer", which are sold only in specialized outlets.

2. The inventory of the assortment of a retail trade enterprise should be supported by the necessary information activities on the part of local authorities. Such activities include ensuring

social priorities in the sale of products of the Samarkand-Prague-Pivo JV, organizational support in establishing relationships with suppliers, providing information support, etc. As you know, the formation and updating of the assortment requires significant financial costs, therefore, an important element of this methodology is the development and use of modern methods and forms of retail trade.

3. In accordance with the master plan for the development of the district, an effective trading network is being formed in each settlement, reflecting the current needs of the inhabitants of this settlement. In order to form a distribution system for JV "Samarkand-Prague-Pivo", it is necessary to create a constantly updated information base containing information about suppliers of goods (regional representatives, dealers, distributors, sales agents), the range of products supplied, delivery times, price and other delivery conditions, as well as all the details of retail trade enterprises carrying out, in the prescribed manner, an inventory of their assortment policy.

4. In accordance with the peculiarities of the characteristics of consumer goods, suppliers enter into direct contracts with interested trading enterprises that are able to fulfill the conditions for the sale of the supplied goods, and further provide guarantees for the necessary assortment and quality of goods in the distribution network.

DISCUSSION

An important element in improving the channels of distribution of products is the development of forms of trade. The products of the joint venture "Samarkand-Prague-Pivo" do not belong to the essential goods, so the company and intermediaries need to bring it to each potential consumer. Based on this, it is necessary to develop such forms of trade as individual trade services, personal sales, purchasing trade, and network marketing.

Table 1.

Proposals for improving the forms of beer trade on the basis of unorganized commercial entrepreneurship

Form of trade	Description
Trade service	A private entrepreneur concludes an agreement with a trade organization for the sale of a range of goods among the population as a sales representative and receives a commission for this. This form of trade is effective in small settlements where there are retail outlets at home.
Personal Selling	Individuals trade at home, that is, they make home visits to buyers, offer various goods provided by the trading company, accept and fulfill pre-orders, including those from the catalogs of the trading company
Purchasing trade	This form represents an equivalent exchange of goods. Representatives of a trading enterprise buy surplus agricultural products from the population and at the same time offer goods of high demand. In this case, the population does not need to visit the dekhkan market.
Multilevel (network) marketing	This form is known as the "pyramidal" variant of personal

selling, in which the firm recruits independent workers who become distributors of its products. These distributors in turn hire other people and sell the product to them, who also hire distributors, and so on. At the heart of the "pyramid" it is necessary to put a retail enterprise.

CONSLUSIONS

At the same time, special importance should be paid to attracting small trading enterprises located in places of congestion of consumers, places of leisure and recreation for the population. The principles of network marketing most fully reflect the nature of the distribution of products of the joint venture "Samarkand-Prague-Pivo". Based on this, we recommend that the company develop these and other modern forms of distribution of goods with the direct participation of retailers.

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